

Research Output Lifecycle

Guidance for the Research Output Management Planning (ROMPi)

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Abstract

Research Data Management (RDM) provides the strategies, guidelines, and measures to manage research outputs. Like a Jigsaw, RDM requires multiple pieces of multidisciplinary knowledge and competencies. Data Management Planning (DMP) is the formal operational tool to handle this complexity dynamically and in a structured way, ensuring compliance with policies and best practices. The Research Output Lifecycle refers to the stages through which research output evolves, from conception to dissemination. A DMP might be considered as a different form of a data lifecycle. [Della Chiesa & Sikder \(2024\)](#)¹ introduced the concept of Research Output Management Planning (ROMPi), where the research output life cycle plays a fundamental role. Hence, this document is a reference toolkit tailored for the Research Output Management Planning (ROMPi) approach to address policy compliance FAIR research output management best practices throughout the project lifecycle.

Introduction

There is a cross-domain and worldwide agreement that publicly funded research knowledge should be openly disseminated^{2,3}. In Europe, this is reflected by several initiatives, such as the European Open Science Cloud⁴ and consortia, such as the National Research Data Infrastructure in Germany⁵. These initiatives are consequently integrated into several high-level mission statements and policies^{6,7,8}. Moreover, the trend toward an Open Data Governance for non-research data is also worth mentioning⁹. Nevertheless, to achieve the objectives of the Open Science initiatives, it is fundamental that Research Data Management (RDM) meets specific requirements and criteria. These guiding

¹ [ROMPi Approach](#)

² [Open Access - Berlin Declaration](#)

³ [Nosek, Brian A., et al. "Promoting an open research culture." Science 348.6242 \(2015\): 1422-1425.](#)

⁴ [European Open Science CLOUD](#)

⁵ [NFDI - Nationale Forschungsdaten Infrastruktur](#)

⁶ [G6 statement on Open Science](#)

⁷ [Guidelines on the Handling of Research Data within the Leibniz Association](#)

⁸ [Horizon Europe and Open Science](#)

⁹ [Open Government Germany . Third National Action Plan 2021-2023](#)

criteria were defined by Wilkinson et al. and are now commonly known as the FAIR principles¹⁰. Research data is the most valuable asset alongside scholars' scientific and analytic competencies¹¹. In RDM, "Data" is an ambiguous definition as it refers to various research products such as datasets, algorithms, software, workflows, methods, and reports, to mention a few. Thus, referring to "*Research Outputs (or Objects)*" better defines the broad heterogeneity of research deliverables. Funding agencies to ensure the return on investment of publicly funded research demands the adoption of a Data Management Plan (DMP), a formal document and deliverable describing the data management strategies and actions taken during the research project lifecycle and beyond. Della Chiesa et al. (2024) suggest performing DMP by adopting a project management perspective with the Research Output Management Planning (ROMPi) approach. Whether adopting traditional DMP or the ROMPi approach, they rely closely on the research output lifecycle steps¹². Hence, this Research Output Lifecycle guidance is a reference toolkit tailored for the ROMPi approach to address policy compliance FAIR research output management best practices throughout the project lifecycle. Please note that RDM practices might vary considerably depending on the project specificity and research domain. Hence, this document provides a good overview but cannot cover all the possible research output lifecycle aspects of a specific project. This document readapts the RDM checklist proposed by the Harvard Longwood RDM working group¹³ and the previous version of the RDM guidance by Della Chiesa (2022).

¹⁰ [Wilkinson, Mark D., et al. "The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship." Scientific data 3.1 \(2016\): 1-9.](#)

¹¹ [Wilson et al., \(2014\). Realizing the Value of a National Asset: Scientific Data. Eos, Vol. 95, No. 50.](#)

¹² [DCC Lifecycle](#)

¹³ [Harvard Longwood - Research Data Management Lifecycle Checklist](#)

Research Output Lifecycle

Design & Planning

Project planning phase

Depending on the funding program, providing a concise overview of data management measures through a traditional Data Management Planning (DMP) or, as Della Chiesa et al. proposed, through a Research Output Management Planning (ROMPi) approach is required. This guidance document follows the ROMPi approach (perhaps already developed at the proposal phase), where WPs, Deliverables, and some RDM actions are briefly described. During the planning phase, a detailed ROMPi must be developed by reviewing the planned WPs and breaking down WPs and Deliverables into their smallest executable component (see sheet 3 of the ROMPi template in Della Chiesa 2023). Each smallest deliverable should be reviewed regarding its research lifecycle (Design & Planning, Collect & Create, Processing & Analyse, Share & Reuse).

Review high-level policies

Reviewing and ensuring compliance with the high-level policies is fundamental in the planning phase (e.g., [Open Science](#), [Open Access](#), [Research Data Handling Guidelines](#), Institutional Data Governance, [Good Scientific Practices](#), [Open and FAIR Data](#), etc.).

Other relevant policies or processes

Some project deliverables might require compliance with other policies and demand that obligations be formalised and documented.

- Data Privacy Policy: GDPR, Data anonymisation, etc.

- Data Sharing Policy: The project or institution's policy requirements might require that data, methods, code, documentation, etc., be freely available at the project end.
 - Data Retention Policy: Researchers or Institutions should guarantee that data is retained for a certain period (usually ten years from the project begins).
 - Adopt any RDM Onboarding procedure for new project staff.
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Depending on the complexity of the project, coaching support might be required.

Stewardship coaching

- Use all the resources the organisation can provide.
 - Get advice from the Research Data Management/Data Stewardship team.
 - Get consulting from the Scientific Communication and Transfer Officers.
 - Seek support from the library on related topics (e.g. Open Access resources).
 - If available, get project management support to plan your project accordingly.
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The first part of any project provides general but fundamental structured and standardised information with persistent identifiers (PIDs), making linking funders, projects, research outputs, researchers, and institutions more straightforward and efficient.

Administrative Information

- [Funder ID](#) (Crossref Funder Registry)
 - Project ID or Grant Identification (Generally provided by the funder).
 - Moreover, it is recommended that a persistent identifier (PID) be created for research projects via [RAiD](#) (Research Activity Identifier.)
 - Project and Data management roles, including their [ORCID](#).
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**ROMPi &
DMP templates**

Della Chiesa et al. 2024 promoted the Research Output Management Planning (ROMPi) approach to link research project management and FAIR research output planning.

Nevertheless, if required, funders provide various templates that guide the creation of a data management plan that follows the traditional questionnaire approach.

Templates/Guidance: [Horizon Europe](#), [Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft \(DFG\)](#), [Bundesministerium für Bildung und Forschung \(BMBF\)](#), [Science Europe DMP guidance](#).
[Several DMP applications assist with this process.](#)

Resources planning

Data management is an eligible cost in the project budget (at the proposal phase). Estimate any expense related to the data management services. (Hardware, software, Human resources, Publication costs). Research Data Management goes beyond the project duration. Hence, planning any eventual cost to manage the data when the project is completed, or any handover should be addressed. Finally, resource planning is essential to assess whether the project has all the assets for successful execution. Thus, ensure the project has the proper resources:

- Hardware: Review if any equipment is required for the project.
 - Software: Review the need for any software-related licenses. Research organisations usually possess licenses/institutional subscriptions. If new software is needed, consider starting the acquisition and bureaucratic workflow at the earliest beginning of the project.
 - Data collection/creation: Assess whether the project has the proper resources for data acquisition, such as staff for field work, fieldwork equipment, data usage rights.
 - Data processing: Evaluate the need for computational resources (e.g. Virtual Machines). Projects with high
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computational requirements might need special dedicated servers or High-Performance Computing (HPC).

- A large consortia project might require a cloud-based collaborative solution.
- Cost for publication: Plan the costs for open access in advance.
- Training: Staff might require training to use equipment or software or to employ workflows. Plan any training at the early stage of the project.

Storage

- Assess if the project has particular requirements in terms of Long-term preservation, Project data storage.

Data organisation & backup

Ensure data organisation best practices are adopted by establishing best practices for folder structure, naming conventions, versioning, and labelling.

- Review and required folder and [naming convention](#) with the staff and project partners
 - Ensure the organisation has a [backup recovery plan](#).
 - Assess if the project has special requirements for Long-term preservation and data storage.
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Data Collection & Creation

Describe the data collection/creation within a [README.txt](#) file.

- E.g. if existing data is collected, provide a link to the data source, URL, DOI, etc., with a link to the metadata (e.g. Title, abstract, creator, license, version, publication date, data format).
- Collect all the relevant metadata during the data collection phase.

Data retrieval

Document the data collection at the workflow level in a README.txt

Describe any protocol, workflow, procedure, preprocessing steps, and methods involved in the data creation. This information is essential as it provides the provenance details of the dataset.

Data type & format

Describe the Data type (e.g. Raster Geodata, Questionnaire, Interviews) and data format (Geotiff, CSV table, ODT/DOC). If possible, adopt open data formats and avoid proprietary file formats. Justify the use of proprietary software for data creation (widespread use and acceptance, researcher competencies, existing purchased license).

Software & tools

Ensure the project has all the tools, equipment, hardware, and software to create and process the data.

Metadata & standards

Metadata is as essential as data itself, should be FAIR, and should always be available with a CC0 license, as it provides structured

information of the context to understand and interpret the data. Data without metadata is of little value. Metadata information is, for example, the Title, abstract, creator, license, version, publication date and data format, to mention a few). Different metadata standards are used in various disciplines. Here are some links to help find a suitable metadata standard for the project.

- [Look for standards by research subject](#) (e.g. Earth Science)
- [Metadata registry from FAIRsharing](#)
- [Metadata directory from Research Data Alliance \(RDA\)](#)
- [Disciplinary Metadata from the Digital Curation Center \(DCC\)](#)

Recommended standard at IOER (general and domain-specific)

- General: [DataCite standard](#), [Dublin core](#), for generic research output metadata description.
- Geoscience: [ISO 19115](#) for describing geographic information.
- Social science: [International metadata standard DDI](#) and [DDI controlled Vocabularies](#) are commonly used for the interview/survey data.

Estimate data volume at the project end, mainly if the project produces a substantial amount of data.

**Data storage
management**

- Review the institutional [storage, backup and recovery strategies](#) to understand whether they satisfy the project requirements.
 - Consult with the IT department to assess the project needs regarding performance, storage size, functionality and access controls.
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- Review the institution's data retention policies to determine how long the data is preserved.
 - Ensure data privacy (research data anonymisation) and access permission and controls for project staff.
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Data Processing & Analysis

Raw and active data

Raw and active datasets refer to all the datasets, documents, and scripts regularly managed at various stages of development and maturity during the project execution. This data is usually not released or published due to its inherently preliminary nature. However, after multiple iterations, preprocessing, and review, this data reaches a sufficient maturity level and becomes analysis-ready. This step is crucial as it is the provenance link between raw and analysis-ready data.

- Ensure that any preprocessing, quality control algorithm or workflow is documented and organised (see the previous section on versioning and naming conventions).

Scripts & algorithms

Data processing, analyses, and model building are commonly executed in a scripting environment using various high-level programming languages such as [R](#), [Python](#), [Matlab](#).

Nowadays, it is common practice to share code and scripts, and it is essential [to adopt coding best practices](#) to harmonise the [coding style](#) and make algorithms easily reusable.

Coding is often a collaborative, dynamic and fast editing practice; therefore, using a version control system to track changes over time and recall a specific version is strongly recommended. [Github](#) and [Gitlab](#) are two very well-established version control systems.

- Create your Github/Gitlab account.

- Create your repository (e.g. [IOER Monitor repository](#))
 - Join the Institution Git organisation eventually.
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Analysis ready dataset

The dataset with a sufficient maturity level (minimum metadata information, documentation, quality control, provenance, etc.) satisfies the minimum requirements for publication in [data repositories](#) and [data journals](#).

- If possible, publish data already at this stage.
 - Assigning a DOI to analysis-ready dataset creates the first step to tracking the provenance of any derived output.
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Workflow, provenance and processes documentation

Numerical models, machine learning, statistical modelling, and analysis-ready datasets are used as input data to produce further outputs (e.g., model output). Therefore, keeping track of the processing steps is a fundamental best practice for collecting provenance information. It also provides the steps to reproduce a research output and share methods (algorithms, code) with other scholars and peers.

- Keep records of processing steps (e.g. a README.txt might be sufficient).
- Version control systems ([Github](#), [Gitlab](#)) are commonly used for cloud collaborative algorithm development, wiki documentation, and code versioning.
- Several editors/IDE provide GIT integration, making coding and versioning straightforward.

Tracking robust and systematic provenance metadata is challenging, some tools can help in provenance tracking.

Literate Programming (Interactive computational notebooks):

- Two of the most popular applications are [Jupyter Notebooks](#) and [RMarkdown](#) (executable example [here](#)).

Computing environment:

- Data science workflow has been greatly improved using containers for packaging software and data ([rules for reproducible science with docker](#)).

Quality control & Quality reporting

Even analysis-ready research data often lack the necessary quality for inclusion in a repository for publication. Thus, supplementary processing and various quality measures might be necessary to meet data quality before their utilisation or publication.

- Data Cleaning and Preprocessing: correcting errors, imputing missing values, and standardising formats to ensure consistency and accuracy.
 - Data validation, cross-validation, sensitivity analysis procedures.
 - Documentation of the quality control measures into a quality report.
 - Assure rich metadata description.
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Preserve, Share & Reuse

Evaluate research data for long-term archiving

Each project is specific in the data retention and preservation requirements.

- Assess whether some data must be retained long-term in institutional servers (e.g. Raw Geodata or statistical base data that can be used in several projects).
- Assess if data must be destroyed at the project ending (e.g. sensitive audio or video interviews).
- Plan what shall be published.

Sharing requirements

Review the data-sharing policies and requirements of the project.

- Although making research data available has become increasingly common, research funding might vary in data-sharing requirements. For example, Horizon Europe is the most demanding, with stringent [Open Science policies](#) such as Open Access, IP and IPR management, Data Management Plan as deliverables, FAIR and open research outputs by default with few exceptions.

Ownership and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR)

Clarify ownership of and rights relating to research data at the project begins. Ownership and rights will determine how the data can be managed, shared, published, and reused.

- Intellectual property (IP) "refers to any asset created by the mind.

- IP can be protected by IPR (Intellectual Property Rights). Copyright is an example of IPR for research outputs such as publications. Copyright is an automatic IPR and does not require formal registration as needed for patents. However, to clarify to others, mark any copyrighted work with the © symbol, the author's name, and the year the work was created.
- Copyright provides ownership. However, in research, it is good scientific practice to allow data reuse by assigning a proper license, which still gives control over any artwork, creating the terms and conditions for reuse.

In project consortia, IP and IPR need to be explicitly agreed to by the parties, as multiple actors and parties might share IP and IPR.

- [Creative Commons licenses](#) are used for research data and publication. While for research output such as open-source software or code, [MIT](#) and [GPL](#) are the most common. [Here](#) are some various licences for software or data.
- [Tool to compare licences](#) with the [European Union Public Licence](#).
- Articles or output published under Open Access (OA) commonly use the CC-BY license.
- CC-BY-SA, CC-BY and CC0 or comparable licenses are considered Open Access licences.

Licenses

Important: [evaluate the compatibility among different licences](#), especially when using several input data with heterogeneous licences. For example, an Inbound CC-BY-NC-SA is incompatible with outbound CC-BY 4.0 as the inbound license is less permissive. Hence, the inbound license of one input dataset can affect the license used for the output.

Metadata information of any research output is always open under [CC0 license](#) (Public domain). Research outputs are not always freely available, but their Metadata describing the dataset must be FAIR.

Metadata sharing

- Search for a suitable (generic or discipline-specific) [repository/catalogue](#) that allows storing metadata information or storing datasets with secure access to the data while showing the metadata.
- Give preferences to domain-specific repositories / catalogues as they adopt specific metadata standard descriptors (see previous section *Data collection & creation* → *Metadata and standards*).

Research code, scripts, algorithms, and software are generally managed with the Github or Gitlab hosting platform for version control, collaboration and sharing.

Code sharing

- Describe the code repository with a [comprehensive README](#)
- [Make Your Code Citable using GitHub and Zenodo](#) (link [the GitHub release with Zenodo](#)).
- Consider publishing a [software description paper](#).

Publish data in trustworthy repositories with a preference for domain-specific repositories. Moreover, data can be well described in ISI peer-reviewed [data journals](#).

Data sharing

- Select the suitable repository.
- If required, ensure data is licensed with the necessary restrictions, embargo time.

Share other research outputs

Share openly (open access) with a persistent identifier (DOI) any other research output using the generic repository Zenodo and eventually create your community for the project (e.g. [Leibniz-IOER Zenodo community](#)).
